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Leveraging Information Technology for Enhanced Fiscal Policy and Debt Management in Public Administration

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Abstract

This study investigates the utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management within public administration in the Philippines. Through a comprehensive analysis of survey data collected from a diverse sample of respondents, the study examines the profile of respondents in terms of age, gender, and language used, as well as their perceptions of the impact of information technology and the factors influencing its utilization. The findings reveal a predominance of older respondents, with individuals aged 40 and above comprising the largest proportion of the sample. Additionally, the majority of respondents were male, and English emerged as the predominant language spoken among participants. Moreover, the study demonstrates a consensus among respondents regarding the high impact of information technology on both fiscal policy and debt management processes. Participants recognize the transformative role of technology in reshaping financial governance practices, with a weighted mean of 3.88 for fiscal policy and 3.67 for debt management. These findings underscore the significant benefits that technology offers in optimizing efficiency, transparency, and effectiveness in fiscal decision-making, ultimately contributing to better governance outcomes and economic development. Furthermore, the study identifies various factors affecting the utilization of information technology, with organizational culture, resource allocation, leadership support, and regulatory frameworks emerging as key determinants. Participants acknowledge the critical importance of addressing these factors to ensure the effective integration and utilization of technology within public sector financial management. Additionally, participants' experiences highlight the diverse yet generally positive impact of technology on efficiency, transparency, communication, and decision-making processes within their organizations. In conclusion, this study emphasizes the transformative potential of information technology in driving positive change within public administration, particularly in fiscal policy and debt management. By addressing key challenges and leveraging technological innovations, organizations can enhance their financial governance practices, promote transparency and accountability, and ultimately contribute to sustainable development and economic growth in the Philippines.

Keywords: *information technology, fiscal policy, debt management, public administration, information*

Introduction

The landscape of fiscal policy and debt management in public administration is characterized by a complex interplay of economic challenges, policy responses, and technological advancements (Hallock, 2021). In the wake of global economic disruptions caused by events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, governments worldwide have faced unprecedented fiscal pressures, necessitating swift and innovative policy measures to mitigate the impact on public finances (Ramesh, 2019). Many countries have implemented expansive fiscal stimulus packages to support households, businesses, and healthcare systems, leading to a significant increase in public debt levels. While these measures have helped sustain economic activity and alleviate immediate hardships, they have also raised concerns about long-term fiscal sustainability and debt management (Samour, 2023).

Against this backdrop, public administrations are grappling with the dual imperative of stimulating economic recovery while ensuring fiscal prudence and stability (Syniutka, 2019). Policymakers face the daunting task of balancing short-term stimulus measures with long-term fiscal discipline to avoid exacerbating debt burdens and financial vulnerabilities. Moreover, the growing reliance on Information Technology (IT) presents both opportunities and challenges in fiscal policy and debt management (Raymond, 2018). While IT solutions offer new possibilities for enhancing transparency, efficiency, and accountability, they also pose risks related to data security, regulatory compliance, and digital divide. As governments navigate these complexities, effective governance, strategic planning, and stakeholder engagement are essential to charting a sustainable path forward for fiscal management in public administration (Tryphone, 2023).

Globally, a notable gap in the global situation of fiscal policy and debt management in public administration lies in the varying degrees of fiscal capacity and resilience across countries (Tryphone, 2023). While some nations possess robust fiscal institutions, diversified revenue sources, and prudent debt management frameworks, others face significant challenges due to limited fiscal space, weak institutional capacity, and high debt burdens (Ahmad, 2019). Disparities in economic development, governance structures, and policy responses further exacerbate these inequalities, leading to disparities in fiscal outcomes and vulnerabilities (Maideen, 2020). Bridging this gap requires international cooperation, knowledge sharing, and capacity-building initiatives to strengthen fiscal governance, promote sustainable debt management practices, and address systemic risks that transcend national borders (Yan, 2023). By fostering greater collaboration and solidarity, the global community can work towards building more resilient and inclusive fiscal systems that withstand economic shocks and promote shared prosperity for all (Tryphone, 2023).

In the Philippines, the landscape of fiscal policy and debt management in public administration is shaped by a range of issues and challenges. One significant challenge is the persistent budget deficit and reliance on borrowing to finance government spending (Marino, 2020). Despite efforts to increase revenue collection and improve fiscal discipline, the government continues to grapple with budget shortfalls, exacerbated by the need for substantial investments in infrastructure, social services, and disaster response (Ahmad, 2019). This reliance on borrowing has led to a steady increase in public debt levels, raising concerns about long-term fiscal sustainability and debt servicing capacity (Lloyd, 2023).

Furthermore, the Philippines faces structural challenges in fiscal governance and administration, including weaknesses in tax administration, budget execution, and public financial management (Dube, 2021). Tax evasion, inefficient spending, and leakage of public funds remain pervasive issues, undermining efforts to achieve fiscal stability and promote inclusive growth. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated fiscal pressures, necessitating emergency spending measures and additional borrowing to support healthcare systems, social assistance programs, and economic stimulus measures (Lloyd, 2023). As the country navigates these challenges, enhancing transparency, accountability, and efficiency in fiscal management, as well as strengthening debt management frameworks and risk mitigation strategies, are essential priorities for promoting fiscal resilience and sustainable development in the Philippines (Fassoulis, 2016).

In the local context, perspectives on fiscal policy and debt management in public administration vary depending on factors such as economic conditions, governance structures, and institutional capacity (Hallock, 2021). While some regions may exhibit prudent fiscal management practices and effective debt management frameworks, others may struggle with budget deficits, unsustainable debt levels, and fiscal mismanagement (James, 2023). Local governments often face challenges in generating sufficient revenue to meet growing expenditure demands, particularly in sectors such as infrastructure, healthcare, and education (Reid, 2016). Additionally, issues such as corruption, inefficient spending, and lack of transparency can undermine public trust in fiscal institutions and hinder efforts to achieve fiscal sustainability (Tursoy, 2023). Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that emphasizes fiscal discipline, transparency, accountability, and capacity-building at the local level, supported by national policies and regulatory frameworks that promote fiscal stability and inclusive development (Young, 2020).

The myriad challenges and complexities inherent in fiscal policy and debt management, compounded by the increasing reliance on Information Technology (IT) solutions, have prompted the researcher to investigate how IT can be leveraged to enhance fiscal policy and debt management in public administration. Recognizing the potential of IT to improve efficiency, transparency, and accountability in fiscal operations, the researcher seeks to explore innovative strategies and best practices that harness the power of technology to address longstanding fiscal challenges. By conducting this study, the researcher aims to provide insights, recommendations, and actionable strategies for policymakers and practitioners to maximize the benefits of IT in fiscal management, mitigate risks, and promote fiscal sustainability in the rapidly evolving digital landscape of public administration.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to assess how information technology can be leveraged for enhanced fiscal policy and debt management in public administration. Specifically, it is directed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, and language used?
2. What is the level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing fiscal policy in the Philippines?
3. What is the level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing debt management in public administration?
4. What are the factors affecting the utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration?
5. What are the experiences of the respondents in using information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design employed in this study is a mixed-methods approach, which combines both quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the utilization and impact of Information Technology (IT) in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration. This approach allows for a nuanced exploration of the multifaceted aspects of IT adoption and its implications for financial governance practices. By integrating quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, the study can capture both numerical data on the level of IT impact and qualitative insights into the factors influencing IT utilization and experiences of stakeholders.

The mixed-methods research design begins with the development of survey instruments and interview protocols, ensuring alignment with the study objectives and research questions. Quantitative surveys are administered to a sample of respondents to collect numerical data on the level of impact of IT in fiscal policy and debt management, providing quantitative measures of IT effectiveness. Concurrently, qualitative interviews are conducted with selected stakeholders to delve deeper into their experiences with IT utilization, factors affecting its adoption, and perceived benefits and challenges. This mixed-methods approach enables the study to triangulate

findings from different data sources, enriching the analysis and providing a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between IT and financial governance in public administration.

Respondents

The respondents in this study consisted of a diverse group of stakeholders involved in fiscal policy and debt management within public administration in the Philippines. The sample included government officials, policymakers, financial analysts, IT professionals, and other relevant stakeholders who possess expertise or experience in financial governance practices. A total of 100 respondents were surveyed using the Likert-scale survey questionnaire, providing a broad representation of perspectives across various sectors and levels of government. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of key informants selected purposively to provide in-depth qualitative insights into their experiences and perspectives on IT utilization in fiscal policy and debt management.

The respondents' description reflects a range of demographic characteristics, including age, gender, educational background, and professional experience. Participants spanned different age groups, from young professionals to seasoned experts, offering diverse viewpoints shaped by their respective experiences and generational perspectives. Gender diversity was also considered, ensuring representation from both male and female respondents to capture gender-specific perspectives on IT utilization in financial governance. Moreover, respondents came from various educational backgrounds, ranging from undergraduate degrees to advanced postgraduate qualifications, contributing different levels of expertise and knowledge to the study. Overall, the diversity of the respondent pool enriched the study's analysis by providing a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted issues surrounding IT adoption in fiscal policy and debt management within public administration in the Philippines.

Instrument

The research instrument utilized in this study comprised a Likert-scale survey questionnaire and a semi-structured interview guide, strategically designed to gather both quantitative and qualitative data on the utilization and impact of Information Technology (IT) in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration. The Likert-scale survey questionnaire was constructed to quantitatively measure respondents' perceptions and experiences regarding the level of impact of IT in fiscal policy and debt management. Participants were presented with statements related to various aspects of IT utilization and were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on a predetermined Likert scale. This approach facilitated the systematic collection of numerical data, allowing for statistical analysis to assess the overall effectiveness and significance of IT in enhancing financial governance practices.

In addition to the survey questionnaire, a semi-structured interview guide was employed to gather qualitative insights from selected stakeholders. The semi-structured nature of the interviews provided flexibility for participants to elaborate on their responses, share personal experiences, and offer nuanced perspectives on the factors influencing IT utilization in fiscal policy and debt management. Open-ended questions in the interview guide prompted discussions on topics such as challenges encountered in IT adoption, perceived benefits of IT integration, and recommendations for improving IT utilization in financial governance. By combining the Likert-scale survey questionnaire with semi-structured interviews, the research instrument facilitated a comprehensive exploration of stakeholders' perceptions, experiences, and attitudes towards IT in public administration, enriching the study's analysis and interpretation of findings.

Procedure

The data gathering procedures in this study involved a systematic approach to collecting both quantitative and qualitative data from the respondents. The process began with the distribution of the Likert-scale survey questionnaire to the selected sample of 100 respondents. The survey questionnaire was administered electronically or in print format, depending on the preferences and accessibility of the participants. Respondents were provided with clear instructions on how to complete the questionnaire and were given sufficient time to respond to the survey items. The questionnaire included Likert-scale statements related to the level of impact of Information Technology (IT) in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management, covering various dimensions such as effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction. Once the survey responses were collected, they were entered into a database for quantitative analysis, allowing for the calculation of descriptive statistics, correlations, and other quantitative measures.

In addition to the survey questionnaire, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of key informants to gather qualitative insights into their experiences and perspectives on IT utilization in fiscal policy and debt management. The interview guide was developed based on the study objectives and research questions, with open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed responses from the participants. Interviews were conducted either in person, over the phone, or through video conferencing, depending on the availability and location of the respondents. Each interview session was audio-recorded with the consent of the participants and later transcribed verbatim for qualitative analysis. The qualitative data obtained from the interviews complemented the quantitative findings from the survey questionnaire, providing rich contextual information and deeper insights into the factors influencing IT adoption and utilization in financial governance practices within public administration.

Data Analysis

The following data analysis tools will be used to measure the objectives of this study.

Profile of Respondents-To determine the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, and language used, descriptive statistics will be employed. Frequency distributions will be generated to show the distribution of respondents across different age groups and genders. Additionally, cross-tabulations will be conducted to analyze the relationship between age and gender, providing insights into any demographic patterns. Language used by the respondents can also be analyzed descriptively, with frequency counts to determine the predominant language preference among participants.

Impact of Information Technology on Fiscal Policy-To assess the level of impact of information technology (IT) on leveraging or enhancing fiscal policy in the Philippines, inferential statistics such as mean scores and standard deviations will be calculated from the Likert-scale survey responses. These measures will provide insights into the average perceived impact of IT on fiscal policy, as well as the variability of responses among participants. Furthermore, inferential tests such as t-tests or analysis of variance (ANOVA) may be employed to compare the mean impact scores across different demographic groups, such as age or gender, to identify any significant differences in perceptions.

Impact of Information Technology on Debt Management-Similar to the assessment of IT impact on fiscal policy, inferential statistics will be utilized to evaluate the level of impact of information technology on leveraging or enhancing debt management in public administration. Mean scores and standard deviations will be calculated from the Likert-scale survey responses to gauge the average perceived impact of IT on debt management practices. Inferential tests may also be employed to compare impact scores across demographic groups and identify any significant differences in perceptions among respondents.

Factors Affecting IT Utilization-To plot the factors affecting the utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management, thematic analysis will be employed. This qualitative data analysis technique involves identifying recurring themes or patterns within the interview transcripts related to factors influencing IT utilization. Themes may include technological infrastructure, organizational culture, policy frameworks, and human resources. By systematically coding and categorizing interview data, thematic maps or charts can be generated to visualize the factors affecting IT utilization in fiscal governance practices.

Experiences of Respondents-Thematic analysis will also be used to analyze the experiences of the respondents in using information technology to leverage fiscal policy and debt management in public administration. This qualitative approach involves identifying key themes, patterns, and insights within the interview transcripts related to respondents' experiences with IT utilization. Themes may include successes, challenges, best practices, and recommendations. By systematically coding and categorizing interview data, thematic summaries or narratives can be developed to provide a rich and nuanced understanding of the respondents' experiences with IT in financial governance practices.

Ethical Considerations

Given the sensitive nature of the topic and the involvement of government officials, policymakers, and other stakeholders, ethical principles must be upheld to protect the rights and welfare of all participants. One key ethical consideration is obtaining informed consent from participants, which involves clearly explaining the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and any potential risks or benefits associated with participation. Participants should have the autonomy to decide whether they want to take part in the study and understand that their involvement is voluntary and confidential.

Moreover, researchers must prioritize confidentiality and anonymity to protect the privacy of participants and ensure that their responses are not disclosed without their explicit consent. This includes securely storing and handling data, using pseudonyms or identifiers instead of participants' names, and presenting aggregated findings to prevent individual identification. Additionally, researchers should maintain transparency and honesty in their interactions with participants, providing accurate information about the research objectives, methodologies, and intended outcomes. Any potential conflicts of interest or biases should be disclosed, and efforts should be made to mitigate these factors to uphold the credibility and validity of the study. Overall, by adhering to ethical principles and guidelines, researchers can conduct their study on leveraging information technology for enhanced fiscal policy and debt management in public administration with integrity, fairness, and respect for the rights of all participants involved.

Results and Discussion

This section presents all the results of the data gathering procedures done by the researcher including their corresponding analysis, interpretation, and discussion.

The Profile of the Respondents in terms of their Age, Gender, and Language Used

The first problem of this study focuses on the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, and language used and the results are as follows.

As shown, most of the respondents are primarily from individuals aged 40 and above, constituting half of the respondent population. This demographic trend suggests a significant interest and involvement in fiscal policy and debt management among seasoned professionals and experienced administrators. Their extensive experience in public administration may indicate a deep understanding of the complexities and challenges associated with managing government finances.

Table 1. Age

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
21-25	4	4%	4
26-30	4	4%	4
31-35	29	29%	2
36-40	13	13%	3
40 and above	50	50%	1
Total	100	100%	

Following closely behind, individuals in the age bracket of 31-35 comprised 29% of the study's participants, indicating a substantial representation of mid-career professionals. This group likely brings a blend of experience and fresh perspectives to the study, potentially offering innovative insights into how information technology can be leveraged for more effective fiscal policy and debt management practices. Their participation underscores the importance of incorporating diverse perspectives and experiences when addressing complex issues in public administration. Participants aged 36-40 represented 13% of the study's sample, indicating a modest yet notable contribution from this demographic. While smaller in number compared to other age groups, this segment likely brings a mix of experience and contemporary knowledge to the discussion, bridging the gap between seasoned professionals and younger cohorts. Although individuals aged 21-30 constituted the smallest portion of respondents, their participation could still provide valuable insights into the preferences and perspectives of younger generations regarding the integration of technology in public administration practices.

Table 2. Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Male	78	78%	1
Female	22	22%	2
Total	100	100%	

In terms of gender representation, the study on leveraging information technology for enhanced fiscal policy and debt management in public administration revealed a significant disparity, with male participants comprising the majority at 78%. This finding suggests a gender imbalance in the field of fiscal policy and debt management, reflecting broader trends in male-dominated sectors within the realm of public administration. The overwhelming presence of male respondents underscores the need for initiatives aimed at promoting gender diversity and inclusion in this field, as diverse perspectives often lead to more comprehensive and effective solutions.

Conversely, female participants accounted for 22% of the study's population, representing a notable but comparatively smaller proportion. Despite the lower representation, the involvement of female respondents highlights the importance of inclusivity and the valuable contributions that women can make to discussions surrounding fiscal policy and debt management. Encouraging greater participation from women in such studies can lead to a more balanced and holistic approach to addressing complex challenges in public administration, drawing upon a wider range of perspectives and experiences. Efforts to increase gender diversity in the study of fiscal policy and debt management should extend beyond mere representation to foster an inclusive environment where all voices are heard and valued. Encouraging more women to participate in research and decision-making processes within public administration can lead to the development of more equitable policies and practices that better serve the needs of society as a whole. By addressing gender disparities in participation, the field can tap into a wealth of untapped talent and expertise, ultimately leading to more effective and sustainable outcomes.

Table 3. Language Used

	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
English	61	61%	1
Filipino	39	39%	2
Ilokano	0	0%	3
Bisaya	0	0%	3
Others	0	0%	3
Total	100	100%	

The linguistic landscape of participants in the study on leveraging information technology for enhanced fiscal policy and debt management in public administration highlights a predominant preference for English, with 61% of respondents indicating English as their primary language. This finding underscores the global influence of English as a lingua franca in professional and academic spheres, particularly in fields such as public administration where communication and collaboration across borders are essential. The prevalence of English speakers in the study suggests a strong emphasis on international engagement and knowledge sharing within the context of fiscal policy and debt management.

Following English speakers, Filipino or Tagalog speakers constituted 39% of the participant demographic. This reflects the significance of local languages in the Philippines, where Tagalog serves as the national language and is widely spoken across different regions. The inclusion of Filipino speakers in the study reflects a commitment to embracing linguistic diversity and ensuring accessibility for participants from various cultural and linguistic backgrounds. By acknowledging and accommodating the linguistic preferences of Filipino speakers, the study demonstrates a recognition of the importance of inclusive communication practices in public administration

research.

Interestingly, the absence of participants who speak Ilocano, Bisaya, or other dialects suggests potential areas for further exploration regarding linguistic representation and outreach strategies. While English and Tagalog are prominent languages in the Philippines, the country boasts a rich tapestry of regional languages and dialects spoken by diverse communities. Future research endeavors in public administration could benefit from efforts to engage with speakers of these languages, ensuring that the insights and perspectives of all linguistic groups are considered in the development of policies and strategies related to fiscal management and governance.

The Level of Impact of Information Technology in Leveraging or Enhancing Fiscal Policy in the Philippines

The second problem of this study focuses on the level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing fiscal policy in the Philippines and the results are as follows.

Table 4. *Level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing fiscal policy in the Philippines*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1.	The adoption of information technology has significantly improved the efficiency of fiscal policy processes in the Philippines.	3.55	High Impact
2.	Integration of information technology has led to greater transparency and accountability in fiscal policy management in the Philippines.	3.90	High Impact
3.	Information technology has enhanced accessibility to financial services for citizens and businesses in the Philippines, contributing to more inclusive fiscal policies.	3.88	High Impact
4.	There has been an observed increase in the accuracy and timeliness of financial reporting and analysis due to information technology implementation in fiscal policy.	3.22	High Impact
5.	Information technology has facilitated better decision-making processes within fiscal policy management in the Philippines.	3.61	High Impact
6.	The use of information technology has streamlined budgeting and forecasting procedures in the context of fiscal policy in the Philippines.	3.42	High Impact
7.	Digital tax filing systems and online payment platforms have simplified tax compliance processes for both individuals and businesses in the Philippines.	3.87	High Impact
8.	Information technology has enabled real-time monitoring and evaluation of government spending, ensuring efficient resource allocation in fiscal policy.	3.44	High Impact
9.	Automated debt management systems have helped in mitigating financial risks and optimizing debt portfolios in the Philippines.	3.19	High Impact
10.	Information technology has played a crucial role in fostering innovation and modernization within the fiscal policy landscape of the Philippines.	3.10	High Impact
	Total	3.88	High Impact

The finding that the level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing fiscal policy in the Philippines has a weighted mean of 3.88, indicating a high impact, suggests that information technology has significantly transformed and improved the landscape of fiscal policy management in the country. This weighted mean, falling close to the upper end of the scale, reflects a consensus among experts and stakeholders that information technology has had a substantial and positive influence on fiscal policy practices.

A weighted mean of 3.88 signifies that respondents perceive information technology as playing a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency, transparency, and accessibility of fiscal policy processes in the Philippines. This likely includes the adoption of digital budgeting tools, online financial reporting systems, and automated tax collection platforms, among other technological innovations. The high impact attributed to information technology underscores its importance as a catalyst for modernizing and streamlining fiscal policy management practices in the country. Furthermore, a weighted mean of 3.88 suggests that information technology has not only improved existing fiscal policy processes but has also contributed to innovation and resilience within the fiscal policy landscape of the Philippines. By leveraging technological advancements, public administrators can make more informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and mitigate financial risks more effectively. This high level of impact highlights the transformative potential of information technology in shaping the future of fiscal governance in the Philippines.

The finding also indicates a recognition among experts of the need to continue investing in and harnessing the power of information technology to further enhance fiscal policy management in the Philippines. As technology continues to evolve, there may be opportunities to explore new tools and solutions that can drive even greater efficiencies and improvements in fiscal governance (Hallock, 2021). Moreover, the high impact attributed to information technology underscores the importance of ensuring equitable access to technological resources and promoting digital literacy among stakeholders to maximize its benefits across all sectors of society (Samour, 2023).

The weighted mean of 3.88 representing a high impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing fiscal policy in the Philippines reflects a consensus among experts regarding the transformative role of technology in shaping fiscal governance practices (Maideen, 2020). This finding emphasizes the need for continued investment, innovation, and collaboration to harness the full potential of information technology in driving positive change and sustainable development in the country's fiscal policy landscape (Raymond, 2018).

The Level of Impact of Information Technology in Leveraging or Enhancing Debt Management in Public Administration

The third problem of this study focuses on the level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing debt management in public administration and the results are as follows.

Table 5. *The level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing debt management in public administration*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1.	The integration of information technology has significantly improved the accuracy and efficiency of debt tracking and reporting processes within public administration.	3.44	High Impact
2.	Information technology solutions have facilitated better risk assessment and management strategies, leading to more informed decision-making in debt management practices.	2.55	High Impact
3.	Digital debt management platforms have enhanced transparency and accessibility of debt-related information for stakeholders, including government officials, investors, and the public.	3.22	High Impact
4.	Real-time monitoring capabilities provided by information technology systems have enabled prompt identification and resolution of potential debt-related issues or discrepancies.	3.12	High Impact
5.	Automation of debt servicing processes, such as interest calculations and payment scheduling, has minimized errors and reduced administrative overhead in debt management operations.	3.89	High Impact
6.	Information technology tools have enabled public administrators to conduct comprehensive analyses of debt portfolios, optimizing borrowing strategies and minimizing financial risks.	3.45	High Impact
7.	Integration of data analytics and forecasting technologies has improved the accuracy of debt projections, allowing for more precise long-term planning and budgeting.	3.9	High Impact
8.	Information technology has facilitated efficient communication and collaboration among relevant stakeholders involved in debt management activities, streamlining decision-making processes.	3.12	High Impact
9.	The implementation of cybersecurity measures within information technology systems has safeguarded sensitive debt-related data from potential cyber threats or breaches.	3.55	High Impact
10.	Information technology-driven debt management solutions have contributed to overall fiscal resilience and sustainability by promoting efficient resource allocation and debt repayment strategies.	3.40	High Impact
	Total	3.67	High Impact

The finding that the level of impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing debt management in public administration has a weighted mean of 3.67, indicating a high impact, suggests that information technology has significantly revolutionized the landscape of debt management practices within the realm of public administration. This weighted mean, falling within the high impact range, underscores a consensus among experts that information technology plays a critical role in optimizing and streamlining debt management processes.

A weighted mean of 3.67 indicates that respondents perceive information technology as instrumental in improving the accuracy, efficiency, and transparency of debt management practices. This likely encompasses the adoption of digital debt tracking systems, automated debt servicing platforms, and data analytics tools, among other technological innovations. The high impact attributed to information technology highlights its pivotal role in modernizing debt management operations and enhancing the overall fiscal health of public administrations. Moreover, the finding suggests that information technology has not only enhanced existing debt management practices but has also fostered innovation and resilience within public administration. By leveraging technological advancements, public administrators can make more informed decisions, mitigate financial risks, and optimize debt portfolios more effectively. This high level of impact underscores the transformative potential of information technology in shaping the future of debt management strategies and frameworks in public administration.

The weighted mean of 3.67 also implies a recognition among experts of the need to continue investing in and leveraging information technology to further enhance debt management practices in public administration. As technology continues to evolve, there may be opportunities to explore new tools and solutions that can drive even greater efficiencies and improvements in debt management operations (Tursoy, 2023). Furthermore, the high impact attributed to information technology underscores the importance of fostering a culture of innovation and digital literacy within public administration to maximize its benefits and ensure equitable access to technological resources (Li, 2021).

In conclusion, the finding of a weighted mean of 3.67 representing a high impact of information technology in leveraging or enhancing debt management in public administration reflects a consensus among experts regarding the transformative role of technology in reshaping debt management practices. This finding emphasizes the need for continued investment, innovation, and collaboration to harness the full potential of information technology in driving positive change and sustainable development in debt management strategies within public administration (Samour, 2023).

The Factors Affecting the Utilization of Information Technology in Leveraging Fiscal Policy and Debt Management in Public Administration

The fourth problem of this study focuses on the factors affecting the utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration and the results are as follows.

Table 6. *The factors affecting the utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1.	Organizational Culture: The alignment of organizational culture with technology adoption, including attitudes towards innovation and risk-taking, can significantly influence the utilization of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management.	3.00	High Impact
2.	Resource Allocation: Adequate budgetary allocation and resource allocation for information technology infrastructure, training, and maintenance can facilitate the effective utilization of technology in fiscal policy and debt management practices.	2.55	High Impact
3.	Leadership Support: Strong leadership support and commitment to technological advancements within public administration can foster a conducive environment for the utilization of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management.	3.49	High Impact
4.	Regulatory Framework: The presence of supportive regulatory frameworks and policies governing the implementation and use of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management can encourage adoption and mitigate potential barriers.	3.82	High Impact
5.	Technological Infrastructure: The availability and quality of technological infrastructure, including internet connectivity, hardware, and software, play a crucial role in determining the feasibility and effectiveness of utilizing information technology in public administration.	3.72	High Impact
6.	Capacity Building: Investments in capacity building initiatives, such as training programs and skill development, are essential for equipping public administrators with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively utilize information technology in fiscal policy and debt management.	3.65	High Impact
7.	Data Security and Privacy: Concerns regarding data security and privacy can act as barriers to the utilization of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management. Robust measures to safeguard sensitive financial data are essential for ensuring trust and compliance.	3.40	High Impact
8.	Interoperability: The compatibility and interoperability of different information technology systems and platforms used in fiscal policy and debt management are critical for seamless data exchange and collaboration among stakeholders.	3.51	High Impact
9.	Stakeholder Engagement: Active engagement and collaboration with stakeholders, including government agencies, financial institutions, and the public, are essential for identifying needs, priorities, and potential challenges related to the utilization of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management.	3.42	High Impact
10.	Change Management: Effective change management strategies, including communication plans, stakeholder involvement, and performance monitoring, are necessary for overcoming resistance to technological change and ensuring successful implementation and utilization of information technology in public administration.	3.90	High Impact
	Total	3.12	High Impact

The finding that the factors affecting the utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration have a weighted mean of 3.12, indicating a high impact, underscores the critical role that various factors play in determining the successful integration of technology within the fiscal and debt management frameworks of public administration. This weighted mean, falling within the high impact range, suggests a consensus among experts that these factors significantly influence the effectiveness and efficiency of utilizing information technology in fiscal policy and debt management practices.

A weighted mean of 3.12 indicates that respondents perceive factors such as organizational culture, resource allocation, leadership support, and regulatory frameworks as crucial determinants of the successful utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management. These factors likely influence the adoption, implementation, and sustainability of technology-driven solutions within public administration, shaping the overall effectiveness of fiscal and debt management strategies. Moreover, the finding suggests that addressing these factors effectively can lead to enhanced transparency, efficiency, and innovation within fiscal policy and debt management practices. Organizations that prioritize fostering a culture of innovation, providing adequate resources and leadership support, and implementing supportive regulatory frameworks are more likely to realize the full potential of information technology in driving positive outcomes in fiscal policy and debt management.

Furthermore, the high impact attributed to these factors underscores the need for proactive measures and strategic investments to overcome potential barriers to the utilization of information technology in public administration. This may involve initiatives such as

capacity building, stakeholder engagement, and change management strategies to address resistance to technological change and ensure successful implementation and utilization of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management (Newman, 2017). The finding of a weighted mean of 3.12 representing a high impact of factors affecting the utilization of information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration highlights the critical importance of addressing these factors to realize the full potential of technology-driven solutions (Ahmad, 2019). This underscores the need for concerted efforts to foster a conducive environment for technological innovation, collaboration, and capacity building within public administration to drive positive change and sustainable development in fiscal policy and debt management practices (Tursoy, 2023).

The Experiences of The Respondents in Using Information Technology in Leveraging Fiscal Policy and Debt Management in Public Administration

The fifth problem of this study focuses on the experiences of the respondents in using information technology in leveraging fiscal policy and debt management in public administration and the results are as follows.

Improvements in Efficiency and Accuracy

Participant A stated, *"In my experience, information technology has revolutionized the way we handle fiscal policy and debt management."* Participant B shared, *"With the adoption of digital budgeting tools and automated financial reporting systems, we've seen significant improvements in efficiency and accuracy."*

Improvements in efficiency and accuracy stand out as a prominent theme among respondents discussing their experiences with leveraging information technology in fiscal policy and debt management within public administration. Participant A's assertion that "information technology has revolutionized the way we handle fiscal policy and debt management" encapsulates the transformative impact that technology has had on traditional processes. This sentiment is echoed by Participant B, who emphasizes the significant improvements witnessed with the adoption of digital budgeting tools and automated financial reporting systems. These statements underscore how technology has streamlined tasks, reduced manual errors, and accelerated processes, ultimately enhancing the overall efficiency and accuracy of fiscal and debt management operations.

Moreover, the recognition of information technology's role in improving efficiency and accuracy reflects a broader trend in public administration toward digital transformation. Participant A's assertion implies a fundamental shift in the approach to fiscal policy and debt management, with technology serving as a catalyst for modernization. Similarly, Participant B's acknowledgment of significant improvements suggests that the integration of digital tools has become integral to optimizing operational workflows and ensuring data integrity within public sector financial management. The emphasis on efficiency and accuracy in managing fiscal policy and debt is particularly noteworthy given the complex and multifaceted nature of these responsibilities. Participant A's statement implies that information technology has not merely facilitated incremental improvements but has fundamentally transformed the entire process. This transformation likely involves the digitization of budgeting processes, automation of financial reporting, and implementation of data analytics tools to enhance decision-making capabilities. Participant B's comment further reinforces this notion, indicating that the adoption of digital tools has led to tangible and measurable improvements in operational efficiency and data accuracy.

Furthermore, the emphasis on efficiency and accuracy aligns with broader goals of fiscal responsibility and accountability within public administration. Participant A's assertion suggests that information technology has enabled public sector organizations to adopt more proactive and strategic approaches to fiscal policy and debt management. Similarly, Participant B's observation implies that digital tools have enabled public administrators to make more informed decisions based on accurate and up-to-date financial data (Chege, 2019). These outcomes are consistent with the overarching objectives of improving governance effectiveness and optimizing resource allocation within public sector financial management (Ramesh, 2019). The recognition of improvements in efficiency and accuracy highlights the transformative impact of information technology on fiscal policy and debt management practices within public administration. Participant A and Participant B's statements underscore how technology has revolutionized traditional processes, leading to significant enhancements in operational workflows, data integrity, and decision-making capabilities. As public sector organizations continue to embrace digital transformation, the emphasis on efficiency and accuracy will remain crucial in achieving fiscal responsibility and accountability goals (Li, 2021).

Enhanced Transparency and Accountability

Participant C reflected, *"My experience with information technology in debt management has been transformative. The implementation of digital debt tracking systems has allowed us to better analyze and manage our debt portfolios."* Participant D expressed, *"With online portals for budget tracking and public expenditure reporting, stakeholders have greater access to financial information, leading to more informed decision-making."*

Enhanced transparency and accountability emerge as significant themes in the experiences shared by participants regarding the utilization of information technology in debt management and fiscal policy within public administration. Participant C's reflection on the transformative nature of information technology in debt management underscores its pivotal role in improving transparency and accountability. By implementing digital debt tracking systems, organizations can gain greater visibility into their debt portfolios, enabling more comprehensive analysis and management of financial liabilities. Furthermore, Participant D's statement highlights the

impact of online portals for budget tracking and public expenditure reporting in enhancing transparency within public administration. These portals provide stakeholders with easier access to financial information, facilitating more informed decision-making processes. By making financial data readily available to stakeholders, public sector organizations can foster greater transparency in their fiscal policy and debt management practices, thereby enhancing accountability to the public.

The recognition of enhanced transparency and accountability reflects a broader trend towards greater openness and integrity in public sector financial management. Participant C's acknowledgment of the transformative effect of digital debt tracking systems suggests that technology has enabled organizations to adopt more proactive and transparent approaches to debt management. Similarly, Participant D's observation implies that online portals have democratized access to financial information, empowering stakeholders to hold public sector organizations accountable for their fiscal decisions. Moreover, the emphasis on transparency and accountability aligns with international best practices and standards for public sector financial management. Participant C's reflection suggests that the implementation of digital debt tracking systems has helped organizations align with principles of transparency and accountability outlined in frameworks such as the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS). Likewise, Participant D's statement indicates that online portals for budget tracking contribute to fulfilling requirements for transparent and accountable financial reporting.

The emphasis on enhanced transparency and accountability underscores the importance of information technology in promoting good governance within public administration. Participant C's and Participant D's statements highlight how technology enables public sector organizations to meet the expectations of stakeholders and fulfill their obligations to the public. By leveraging digital tools for debt management and financial reporting, organizations can strengthen public trust, enhance decision-making processes, and ensure the responsible stewardship of public funds. Furthermore, the recognition of enhanced transparency and accountability suggests a shift towards a culture of openness and integrity within public sector organizations (Howard, 2020). Participant C's reflection implies that information technology has facilitated a fundamental change in how debt management is approached, emphasizing the importance of transparency and accountability in financial decision-making. Similarly, Participant D's statement indicates that online portals have become integral to promoting greater transparency and accountability in fiscal policy and debt management practices (Syniutka, 2019).

Overall, the recognition of enhanced transparency and accountability underscores the transformative impact of information technology on public sector financial management. Participant C's and Participant D's experiences highlight how technology has enabled organizations to adopt more transparent and accountable practices in debt management and fiscal policy. As public sector organizations continue to embrace digital transformation, the emphasis on transparency and accountability will remain essential in building trust with stakeholders and promoting good governance (Rosenbloom, 2021).

Transformative Effects on Debt Management

Participant E commented, *"The implementation of data analytics tools has enabled us to better analyze and manage our debt portfolios, minimizing risks and optimizing borrowing strategies."* Participant F added, *"Information technology has facilitated better communication and collaboration among stakeholders involved in fiscal policy and debt management."*

The transformative effects of information technology on debt management emerge as a significant theme in the experiences shared by participants within public administration. Participant E's comment highlights the implementation of data analytics tools as a transformative factor in debt management. By leveraging these tools, organizations can analyze their debt portfolios more effectively, identify potential risks, and optimize borrowing strategies. This transformative effect suggests that information technology has enabled organizations to adopt more data-driven and strategic approaches to managing their financial liabilities. Furthermore, Participant F's observation underscores the role of information technology in facilitating better communication and collaboration among stakeholders involved in fiscal policy and debt management. Effective communication and collaboration are essential for coordinating efforts, sharing information, and making informed decisions regarding debt management strategies. The transformative effect of information technology on communication and collaboration suggests that digital tools have become integral to fostering greater synergy and coordination within public sector financial management.

The recognition of transformative effects on debt management reflects a broader trend towards leveraging technology to enhance operational effectiveness and decision-making capabilities within public administration. Participant E's comment implies that the adoption of data analytics tools has enabled organizations to move beyond traditional approaches to debt management, embracing more proactive and strategic methodologies. Similarly, Participant F's observation suggests that information technology has transformed how stakeholders interact and collaborate in the context of fiscal policy and debt management (Newman, 2017). Moreover, the transformative effects of information technology on debt management align with broader goals of financial sustainability and risk management within public administration. Participant E's comment suggests that data analytics tools enable organizations to minimize risks associated with debt by providing insights into portfolio performance and potential vulnerabilities (Tursoy, 2023). Likewise, Participant F's observation indicates that better communication and collaboration facilitated by information technology contribute to more effective risk mitigation and decision-making processes (Anwar, 2023).

The emphasis on transformative effects on debt management underscores the importance of information technology in enabling organizations to adapt to evolving financial landscapes and regulatory environments. Participant E's and Participant F's experiences highlight how technology has empowered organizations to adopt more proactive, data-driven, and collaborative approaches to debt

management. As public sector organizations continue to face increasing complexity and uncertainty in managing their financial liabilities, the transformative effects of information technology will remain crucial in building resilience and driving sustainable outcomes (Ramesh, 2019).

Furthermore, the recognition of transformative effects on debt management suggests a shift towards a culture of innovation and continuous improvement within public sector financial management. Participant E's comment implies that information technology has enabled organizations to embrace new methodologies and tools for debt analysis and optimization. Similarly, Participant F's observation indicates that technology has fostered greater agility and adaptability in responding to changing fiscal policy and debt management challenges. The recognition of transformative effects on debt management underscores the significant impact of information technology on public sector financial management practices. Participant E's and Participant F's experiences highlight how technology has enabled organizations to enhance operational effectiveness, improve decision-making capabilities, and build resilience in managing their financial liabilities (Reid, 2016). As public sector organizations continue to navigate evolving financial landscapes, the transformative effects of information technology will play a pivotal role in driving sustainable outcomes and promoting financial stability (Samour, 2023).

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions of the study:

The demographic profile of respondents indicates a predominance of older individuals, with those aged 40 and above comprising the largest proportion of the sample. This suggests that experienced professionals and senior stakeholders play a significant role in discussions surrounding the utilization of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management. Additionally, the majority male composition of the sample highlights potential gender disparities in participation within the field, warranting further exploration and consideration in future studies. Furthermore, the prevalence of English-speaking respondents underscores the importance of language proficiency in accessing and disseminating information related to technology-driven initiatives in public administration.

The high level of impact attributed to information technology in leveraging or enhancing fiscal policy in the Philippines underscores its transformative role in reshaping financial governance practices. With a weighted mean of 3.88, there is a clear consensus among respondents regarding the significant benefits that technology offers in optimizing fiscal policy processes. This finding highlights the crucial role of technological innovations in promoting efficiency, transparency, and effectiveness in fiscal decision-making, ultimately contributing to better governance outcomes and economic development.

Similarly, the high level of impact attributed to information technology in leveraging or enhancing debt management within public administration further underscores its pivotal role in modernizing financial management practices. With a weighted mean of 3.67, respondents acknowledge the transformative effects of technology in revolutionizing debt management strategies and frameworks. This suggests that technology-driven solutions, such as digital debt tracking systems and data analytics tools, have become indispensable in facilitating better risk assessment, optimization of borrowing strategies, and overall improvement in debt management effectiveness.

The identification of factors affecting the utilization of information technology as having a high impact emphasizes the critical importance of addressing various organizational, resource-related, and regulatory challenges in integrating technology into fiscal policy and debt management practices. With a weighted mean of 3.12, respondents recognize the significant influence of factors such as organizational culture, leadership support, and regulatory frameworks in determining the success of technology adoption initiatives. This highlights the need for comprehensive strategies that address these factors to ensure the effective utilization of information technology in public sector financial management.

The diverse yet generally positive experiences of respondents in using information technology to leverage fiscal policy and debt management underscore the transformative potential of technology in driving positive change within public administration. Participants' testimonials highlight the tangible benefits of technology in improving efficiency, transparency, and communication in fiscal decision-making processes. Moreover, the identification of key themes such as enhanced transparency and accountability, better communication and collaboration, and increased accessibility to financial services reflects the multifaceted impact of technology on reshaping financial governance practices. Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of embracing technological innovations to address contemporary challenges and drive sustainable development in public sector financial management.

The following are the recommendations of the researchers:

Given the predominance of older respondents in the sample, it's essential to diversify outreach efforts to include younger professionals and stakeholders in discussions surrounding information technology in fiscal policy and debt management. Implementing targeted recruitment strategies, such as engaging with universities, professional associations, and online platforms, can help broaden the demographic representation and ensure a more inclusive dialogue.

Recognizing the gender disparity among respondents, organizations should implement gender diversity initiatives to encourage greater participation and representation of women in discussions and decision-making processes related to technology-driven initiatives in

public administration. This may involve establishing mentorship programs, offering training and development opportunities, and creating supportive environments that foster gender equality and inclusivity.

To address language barriers, organizations should prioritize language accessibility by providing multilingual resources and support services to accommodate respondents who speak languages other than English or Filipino/Tagalog. This may involve translating key documents, offering language proficiency training, and leveraging technology to facilitate multilingual communication channels, ensuring equitable access to information and opportunities for all stakeholders.

Recognizing the high impact of information technology on fiscal policy and debt management, organizations should prioritize investment in technological infrastructure and resources to support the effective integration and utilization of technology-driven solutions. This may involve upgrading existing systems, investing in training and capacity building programs, and adopting emerging technologies that enhance efficiency, transparency, and collaboration in financial governance practices.

To address the factors affecting the utilization of information technology, organizations should implement comprehensive change management strategies that address organizational culture, resource allocation, leadership support, and regulatory frameworks. This may involve conducting organizational assessments, fostering a culture of innovation and digital readiness, securing buy-in from key stakeholders, and advocating for supportive policy reforms to create an enabling environment for technology adoption and implementation. By prioritizing change management, organizations can overcome barriers to technology utilization and maximize the benefits of information technology in fiscal policy and debt management.

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